

Rehabilitation of Completely Edentulous Xerostomic Patient with Functional Salivary Reservoir

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A 60 year old female patient reported to the department with loose denture and dry mouth. Patient had undergone radiotherapy for SCC of floor of the mouth 1 year back.

Treatment Plan: Complete denture fabrication with functional salivary reservoir in maxillary denture

Intra-oral photograph of shiny and dry completely edentulous maxillary and mandibular arch

Primary impression made using alginiate

Border moulding done using green stick and secondary impression made using alginiate

Try-in done and palatogram obtained

Reservoir boundary made using sprue wax and index made using bioplast sheet

Cured complete dentures

Reservoir index made and reservoir lid made using soft bioplast sheet

Reservoir lid adapted over cured denture

Insertion of denture

Main advantage of using this technique of functional reservoir is slow and sustained release of saliva during functional movements like tongue movement, sucking and swallowing along with easy cleaning of the reservoir. The reservoir space was assessed using palatogram which ensured speech clarity.